

7th
ANNUAL
REPORT

for the period ending June 30, 1963

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
1025 Connecticut Avenue, N.W. Washington 6, D. C.

Ides hic, Spectator Candide, veram delineationem Bibliothecae Publicae celeberrimae Academiae Lugduno-Batavae, prout in usum Republicae (praecipue tamen Doctorum virorum & Studiosorum publicitus instituta est: quae ingenti numero variorum & insignium librorum

*Itala, quos tellus, quos quondam Graecia novit
Hos omnes doctos hic locus unus habet*

*Geologicorum, Iuridicorum, Medicorum, Philosophicorum,
Historicorum, Mathematicorum, aliarumque scientiarum
& artium, ut etiam diversarum linguarum, Hebraica,
Chaldaica, Syriaca, Arabica, Graeca, Latina, Italica, Gallica,
Hispanica, Germanica, Belgica, &c. egregie instructa
est.*

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* Mr. Black served as a member of the Executive Committee through November 14, 1962. He has been succeeded by Dr. Morris.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent non-profit body incorporated in the District of Columbia with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established in 1956 at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

Late in 1960 the Ford Foundation approved a new grant of eight million dollars to enable the Council to continue for an additional seven-to-ten year period its programs of research and demonstration toward the solution of library problems, and at the same time further to concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval of information through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized scientific personnel.

The Council conducts its work chiefly through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

THE COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES

Bibliography and the Mechanization of Library Operations

Books form the stock-in-trade of libraries, but the techniques with which the book-stock is made serviceable are those of bibliography. A great collection of books, lacking bibliographic organization, possesses only potential or accidental usefulness. By contrast, even a tiny collection can render effective and even specialized service, multiplying its own resources through the techniques and tools of bibliography so as to give its users access to worlds of books beyond its own doors.

It is not surprising, therefore, to find that improvement in library service has advanced in step with the availability of important bibliographic tools and services. The profound effect of Dewey's *Decimal Classification* (1876-), of the *Index-Catalogue of the Library of the Surgeon General's Office* (1880-), of the Library of Congress catalog card distribution service (1901-), of Pollard and Redgrave's *Short-Title Catalogue of Books Printed in England* (1926), to cite examples at random, is too well known to require description. But these are only a few out of the many thousands of bibliographic services upon which library work is completely dependent.

It would appear, in consequence, that one of the most direct methods for improving library work is to improve the bibliographic bases upon which it rests. As to the validity of this

conclusion, there can be little doubt, but to act on it is not a simple matter. In the first place, bibliographic operations are expensive, and to mobilize the financial support with which to sustain them requires the preliminary development of a common denominator of need to create a market. But to create this common denominator of need itself commonly involves lengthy preliminaries in the establishment of standards and the adoption of common practices. In addition, the economic execution of a plan must often await improvements in technology.

Thus, although the Smithsonian Institution attempted to create a central source of cataloging information for American libraries as early as 1850, the idea did not achieve success until more than fifty years later with the Library of Congress catalog card distribution scheme in 1901. But in the meantime the common denominator of need developed, standards of cataloging practice were established, and a new technology of catalog maintenance, based upon the catalog card accompanied by its own set of standards and common practices, came into being.

Similar circumstances have affected the development of many of the important bibliographic services upon which libraries depend.

In spite of its fundamental importance for library work, bibliography is frequently held in low esteem even by those to whom the final result, in terms of library service, is important. This is understandable. Bibliographies are myriad (see, for example, the account of the *World Bibliography of Bibliographies* which appears later in these pages); and while some are of such importance that entire professions or industries are dependent upon them, the great majority are specialized and relatively ephemeral publications whose usefulness is limited to a few; and it is the latter which dominate the scene.

The Council early decided to support bibliographic projects only if they should promise results of the widest and most general usefulness or the development of novel techniques of general applicability. Following this policy, the number of bibliographic projects which it has supported have been few.

An example of the first kind was the establishment at the Library of Congress, commencing in 1958, of the National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections. In this instance, also, action had been deferred for many years for want of the

common denominator of need and practice and of an adequate technology. The want of a central record of the scattered manuscript resources for historical research had been expressed continuously for nearly a century. This need gathered urgency as the depositories of manuscripts and the quantities of their holdings multiplied. Only within the past decade, however, was agreement reached as to the method of cataloging these collections so as to make a central record not only useful but feasible. In the meantime, the technique of the "unit" catalog card had become familiar, and the project was consequently launched with the expectation not only that it might result in a central catalog on cards at the Library of Congress, but that similar card files might be duplicated anywhere. In the event, the expectation was exceeded, as the result of a further technological advance. Once the cards were printed, it was possible to reproduce them by photolithography in book form, and as a result a first volume of the Catalog, listing and indexing 7,300 collections in 400 depositories was published in 1962 at no expense to the project, and at a price which is less than one percent of what a set of the cards would have cost.

Two additional volumes of the Catalog will go to press during the present calendar year, raising the number of collections cataloged to 12,330, and containing a revised and greatly improved index to the entire corpus.

As the project stands today, it is well begun, but hardly more than half done. It was originally hoped that when the major portion of the existing manuscript collections had been cataloged the project might continue as a routine operation without outside funding. After the expenditure of three hundred thousands of dollars it is apparent that a considerable effort is still needed to reach the point of routine operation. It would be lamentable if so important a bibliographic service to historical inquiries of every kind should be suspended at this point.

An example of the second sort of bibliographic project — where the objective was the improvement of technique — was one conducted in 1958-1960 for mechanizing the production of printer's copy for the *Index Medicus*. This cumulative bibliography, prepared by the National Library of Medicine, provides the principal record of the journal literature of the medical sciences, and forms the largest current bibliography of any single subject, in terms of numbers of articles indexed (ca.

150,000 in 1962). The improved system which was put into effect in 1961 involved the use of tape-operated typewriters, machine-sorted punched cards and a "sequential" camera; it substantially expedited the publication of the *Index*, effected much-needed improvement in its arrangement and convenience for use, and permitted necessary expansion.

These advances were no sooner effected, however, than the Library, this time with funding from official sources, began to investigate, in its Medlars project, the possibilities of still further improvement by bringing a computer into the operation. Specifically, it was hoped that the speed and flexibility of a computer might make possible machine searches and special listings based on the bibliographic record which the more limited capabilities of punched-card sorting systems do not permit. This enterprise, the costs of which have been many times those of the earlier project, is now coming to a successful conclusion and constitutes the outstanding achievement to date in mechanizing a bibliographic operation, with important implications for many aspects of library work.

For a quarter of a century it has been possible to process bibliographic information with the use of punched cards which can be sorted, selected and printed out by electrical accounting machines. There have been individually successful applications of the punched-card technique, notably in the production of book catalogs for the branches of public library systems. But the range of application has been severely limited by the small font of type available to these machines, restricted to numerals, a few symbols and — in the case of the alphabet — to capital letters only. Even when the speed and manipulative ability of the card-sorting machines was later greatly surpassed by the computers, these typographical limitations persisted.

The Medlars development breaks through this barrier. By providing the computer with a capability of printing its results in a font of 226 characters at a rate of 500 characters a minute, it is able at last to bring the special competences of the computer not only to the editorial processes associated with the compilation and publication of a major bibliographic service, but also to complicated searches of the expanding literature of an important subject, and to special listings resulting from such searches.

The significance of this development consists in this — that

the computer can now speak in the cultivated language of bibliography, and not merely, as hitherto, in a bibliographic pidgin-English. The immediate consequence is to open up the possibilities of dissemination, in machine-readable form, of bibliographic information which individual libraries will be able to apply to local uses for the printing of accession-lists, catalogs and catalog cards, for the preparation of their many other records which are based on bibliographic information such as order lists and circulation records, and eventually perhaps for mechanized bibliographic searching which will supplement or even replace present practices based on printed books and card catalogs.

The immediate consequence is indeed to open up these and still further possibilities. But it cannot be expected that the possibilities will be immediately realized. The situation is much as it was at a point in time intermediate between the initial unsuccessful attempt, previously mentioned, to provide a central cataloging service in 1850 and the final success in 1901. The elements of an automated bibliographic technique have now been developed, but much remains to be done to develop the common denominators of need and potential use, the standards of machine language and of bibliographic information in machine-readable form, the computer programs which will make local use possible, not to mention the necessary bases of financing, all of which will be necessary before these elements can sustain a system.

Progress in these matters may be expected to be rapidly pursued. The stakes are high. They are none other than the pooling of bibliographic resources for library work — and ultimately of the collections which this bibliographic information represents — over wide areas, even nation-wide, in a machine-readable form in which they can be shared and used by methods as seemingly simple as the dialing of a telephone.

Summary of Operation in 1963. Thirty-eight grants, contracts and other allocations were made by the Council during 1963. These totalled \$985,203. Twenty of the allocations were for new projects; eighteen were extensions or renewals of previously-supported projects.

The following pages briefly describe the projects assisted during the past year as well as the results of projects completed.

VERNER W. CLAPP
President

I. BIBLIOGRAPHIC APPARATUS AND TECHNIQUES

(The ultimate objective of library work is to put into the hands of an inquirer a document or an item of information responding to his need. The techniques and apparatus by which the appropriate document or information is identified are those of bibliography. The apparatus includes systems of classification, catalogs, indexes and bibliographies of many kinds, including new varieties in the form of punched cards and computers. The techniques include the arts both of constructing and using the apparatus. A number of the Council's projects during the past year have been concerned with improvement or development in both areas.)

Access to Legal Information. Probably no profession is more dependent upon its literature than is the law, and for this reason the law is better supplied with indexes and other bibliographic aids than perhaps any other profession. But so voluminous is the literature of the law, and so complex and ramifying are many of the questions for which precedents are needed, that even with the available apparatus, searches are likely to be prolonged, expensive and unfruitful. A number of improvements of the search apparatus have been proposed, and the Council has provided assistance in demonstrating several of them.

Indexing Statute Law by Computer. In 1960 the Health Law Center of the Graduate School of Public Health of the University of Pittsburgh, under the direction of Mr. John F. Harty, undertook an experiment in the indexing of statute law by computer.¹ The text of the Pennsylvania statutes was entered on computer tape and searches were programmed. The project, which has recently been completed, suggests that for some purposes at least computer searching of statutory law can be very valuable, specifically the kind of search for which traditional indexes make no provision. As an illustration, the computer was able to conduct for the Attorney General of Pennsylvania a search for all laws referring to the commencement of the fiscal year of Pennsylvania school districts. If

¹ V: 15-16. (Citations in this form are to the Council's annual reports; in the present instance to its *Fifth Annual Report*, pages 15-16.)

done manually, the search would have required a page-by-page examination of the code. In another instance the computer was able to provide the Pennsylvania State and Local Welfare Commission and Department of Justice, at a cost of about \$5,000, with a collation of laws relating to welfare. Professional fees alone for a manual search would have amounted to about \$35,000, or more, according to the two agencies' estimate. It is calculated that the cost of a computer search of the State's code, on the basis of computer time alone and when searches are batched, is approximately \$25 per search.

The final report, publication of which is pending, records the techniques used in the project and problems encountered. Meanwhile several publications have emanated from the project.²

Indexing Case Law by Computer. The American Bar Foundation and the International Business Machines Corporation have for some time been engaged in a joint study of the possibilities of employing computers for the storage, indexing and retrieval of judicial decisions. A completely automated procedure for indexing the materials, based on a thesaurus constructed by computer from the full text of more than five thousand judicial opinions recorded on magnetic tape, is envisaged. A grant has been made to the Foundation which will be used for the preparation of the magnetic tapes which are essential to the first developmental steps in the project. Findings of the project, when completed, are expected to be applicable, perhaps with modifications, to the information problems of the physical sciences, social sciences and humanities.

"Coordinate" Indexing of Legal Literature. As previously reported,³ the Council has supported a two-part inquiry into the practicality of a system for searching legal literature based upon "coordinate" indexing. This method of indexing has become familiar through the use of machine-sorted punched

² William B. Kehl, John F. Horthy, Charles R. T. Bacon and Davis S. Mitchell: An Information Retrieval Language for Legal Studies. *Communications of the Association for Computing Machinery*, 4: 380-389. September 1961. E. M. Fels: Evaluation of the Performance of an Information-Retrieval System by Modified Mooers Plan. *American Documentation*, 14: 28-34. January 1963. Orrin G. Hatch: Good Faith Under the Uniform Commercial Code. *University of Pittsburgh Law Review*, 23: 754-767.

³ V: 16; VI: 19-20.

cards, in which the several attributes of objects or persons are separately coded. Just as Cartesian coordinates make possible the unique definition of a point in space by specifying two or more attributes of linear measurement, so with a punched-card system it is simple to identify from a large group the single person possessing, for example, the attributes "electrical engineer," "between the ages of 30 and 35," and "speaks German."

"Coordinate" indexes can take many forms — edge-notched cards, machine-sorted punched cards, superimposable punched cards, computers, et cetera. In the project supported by the Council, it was hoped that a system which would prove inexpensive to the user, yet would give him complete control of the index (as contrasted with his dependence upon a computer center) might be obtained by entering the index on superimposable punched cards which could then be reduced to microfilm for inexpensive dissemination and consumer use.

To carry out the project it was necessary (a) to prepare a "coordinate" index to a body of law sufficiently large to make comparison with conventional indexes possible and rewarding, and (b) to develop the mechanical devices for entering the index on superimposable punched cards, for reducing these cards to microfilm, and for employing the index in that form.

In consequence, the Council entered into a contract with three law publishers, the Michie Company, Matthew Bender & Company, Inc., and the Bureau of National Affairs, Inc., to prepare a "coordinate" index to the law of motor carriers. This index was prepared under the supervision of Mr. W. H. B. Thomas and was delivered during the past year. It has been converted to superimposable punched cards ("Termatex" cards) by Jonker Business Machines, Inc., which has also developed the special devices for reducing these cards to microfilm and for consulting the resultant microfilm.

Meanwhile, the American Association of Law Libraries has appointed a committee to supervise a series of tests to compare the "coordinate" index with conventional indexes. As the year closed, a series of tests was being conducted; these remain to be evaluated.

List of Legal Subject Headings. For some years the American Association of Law Libraries Committee on Cataloging and Classification has been working on the compilation of a list of subject headings for legal materials. The function of the

list will be to serve both as an aid in the subject cataloging of law materials and as a first step in the development of principles for the construction of new subject headings and subject subdivisions. It is intended to be a self-contained tool for the use of catalogers. In 1960 the Council made a grant to further work on the list,⁴ by employing a technique of compilation based on the use of the "sequential camera" — a variety of camera which can compose printer's reproduction copy in page form by the sequential copying of separate lines of text from IBM cards. The intention was to ascertain to what extent the use of this technique would facilitate the editing and checking and — later — the production of new editions of compilations of this type.

The operation consisted in extracting on cards the legal subject headings from the Library of Congress' general list, preparing a checking edition with the aid of the sequential camera, distributing the checking edition to a corps of associate editors, revising the cards in accordance with the editing, and preparing final printer's copy with the camera. The result has appeared in a substantial work,⁵ and a report on the effectiveness of the sequential camera technique for publications of this kind is expected.

Computer Control of Serial Records. The term "serials" includes all publications (such as periodicals) which are published serially. In the Serial Record are typically brought together, in large libraries, as many activities with respect to serials as possible. Here they are checked in and routed to their destinations; issues found to be missing are claimed; title pages and indexes are also demanded and united with their respective volumes; the binding of completed volumes is controlled and recorded; subscriptions are renewed and payment recorded; and information on the library's serial holdings is dispensed.

Because of the vagaries and complexities of serial publications, serial record work, which might be supposed to involve merely clerical routines, is complicated and expensive. In-

⁴ IV: 15.

⁵ Werner B. Ellinger, editor: *Subject Headings for the Literature of Law and International Law*, South Hackensack, New Jersey: Published for the American Association of Law Libraries by Fred B. Rothman & Co., 1963. 380 p. (AALL Publications Series No. 6).

numerable attempts have been made, without success, to reduce the work to machine-like simplicity and efficiency.

At the University of California at San Diego, a new library is arising, but there is already a computer center on the campus. The librarian, Mr. Melvin J. Voigt, has made an initial attempt, while the number of serials which he was receiving was still small (under a thousand in number) to ascertain the applicability of computer techniques to serial record management. These initial inquiries were promising; the Council has made it possible for him to continue his work and to compare the costs of a computer system with conventional manual practice. A successful venture in this area would prove of wide benefit.

Standards of Cataloging. The Council has continued its assistance, commenced late in 1960, to the Catalog Code Revision Committee of the American Library Association to enable it to bring to a conclusion the revision of the rules for author and title entries begun a decade ago. The work is being carried out in close association with the Library of Congress, which has given the Chief of its Descriptive Cataloging Division, Mr. Sumner Spalding, a leave of absence to serve as editor. Just as the American Library Association's catalog code of 1908 was given general acceptance throughout the English-speaking world as an Anglo-American Code, so it is hoped that the revised rules may also gain similar international acceptance, and arrangements have been made to involve the United Kingdom and other English-speaking countries in the work. At the same time every effort will be made to comply, as fully as possible, with the agreement reached at the International Conference on the Principles of Cataloging, Paris, 1961, to which the Council gave principal support.

The Dewey Decimal System Overseas. The Dewey Decimal Classification is a scheme primarily intended to facilitate the shelf arrangement of books by subject, but it is also widely used for the arrangement of bibliographies and book lists. It was devised by Melvil Dewey and first published in 1876. Soon thereafter it was in wide use and frequently published revisions have continued its usefulness. At present it is the most used classification system not only in the United States, for which it was originally formulated, but also in the United Kingdom and other English-speaking countries. It has been developed for bibliographic purposes by the International

Federation for Documentation as the Universal Decimal Classification, and has been adapted to local needs in a number of countries such as Japan.

The significance of the Dewey Decimal Classification derives from the fact that it has facilitated the classified collection, arranged by subject in accordance with a standardized and easily comprehensible scheme. The classified collection, in turn, has made "open access" possible — perhaps the most typical American contribution to library work. "Open access," based upon classified collections, represents, in a sense, democracy in the library. It is this development which many other nations are now anxious to emulate.

In response to requests for expansions and adaptations of the Classification which will meet the needs of other cultures, the Council has made a grant to the American Library Association toward the cost of a field study abroad. The Council's grant is in addition to appropriations from the Asia Foundation and the non-profit Forest Press, Inc., publisher of the Dewey Decimal Classification and a subsidiary of the Lake Placid Club Education Foundation. The survey will be under the direction of a steering committee representing the American Library Association and its International Relations Committee, Forest Press, the Library of Congress, and the Decimal Classification Editorial Policy Committee. Various countries in the Far East and elsewhere in the world will be visited in the course of the survey.

International Inventory of Musical Sources. Music, the published form of which has been largely the product of the engraver's rather than of the printer's art, has been neglected in the national and international bibliographies. Recently, a genuinely international effort has developed, under the joint auspices of the International Musicological Society and the International Association of Music Libraries, to supply the deficiency through the publication of an *International Inventory of Musical Sources*, through the eighteenth century, in some thirty volumes.

The Council this past year supplemented previous grants to aid the work of the *Inventory* with a second appropriation to further American participation in the project.⁶ Approximately

⁶ V: 19; VI: 14-15.

150 American institutions are cooperating in preparation of the bibliography by submitting records of their music holdings to the American secretariat at the Library of Congress, which processes the records and forwards them to the central secretariats in Paris and Kassel, West Germany. As of June 30, 1963, approximately 30,000 cards, representing holdings in one-hundred-and-fifty-five libraries in the United States, had been forwarded. A number of unique items are coming to light as a result of the checking of American collections. While the number will not be known until the *Inventory* is completed, the first published volume, which lists 17th and 18th century anthologies, disclosed approximately a score of unique works preserved in the United States. Altogether, about 1300 libraries in twenty-five nations are participating in the project.

American Library Resources. With the aid of a previously reported grant to the American Library Association, a supplement to *American Library Resources: A Bibliographical Guide*, prepared by Robert B. Downs and published in 1951, appeared in 1962.⁷ The new work lists 2,818 printed library catalogs, union lists of books and periodicals, descriptions of special collections, surveys of library holdings, calendars of archives and manuscripts, and selected library reports.⁸ The new work by Dr. Downs, Dean of Library Administration at the University of Illinois, lists half as many items for the period 1950-1961 as did the original work for the period from about 1875 to 1950.

World Bibliography of Bibliographies. Dr. Theodore Besterman of the Institut et Musée Voltaire, Les Délices, Geneva, having completed the manuscript for the ninety-eighth and allegedly final volume of his edition of Voltaire's Correspondence, has undertaken once more to reflect, in a new edition of his *World Bibliography of Bibliographies*, the steady increase of work in this form. The first edition of the *Bibliography* was in 1939-1940, 2 volumes, perhaps 25,000 entries; the 2d, 1947-1949, 3 volumes, 63,776 entries; the 3d, 1955-1956, 4 volumes, 84,403 entries. The Council has provided Dr. Besterman with modest assistance to enable him to scan the shelves of the Bibliothèque Nationale (Paris), the British Museum and the Library of Congress for material for a fourth edition.

⁷ V: 19.

⁸ Robert B. Downs: *American Library Resources, A Bibliographical Supplement 1950-1961*. Chicago: American Library Association, 1962. viii, 226 p.

II. PHYSICAL ACCESS

(The bibliographic apparatus is merely a means to an end. Ultimately, the cited manuscript, book or periodical must be seen and consulted, either in original form or in some acceptable facsimile.)

The most satisfactory avenue to physical access to needed library materials is through a comprehensive collection close at hand. The adequacy of acquisitions procedures, including the practices of the book trade and the mechanisms of book procurement obviously affect the contents of individual library collections and consequently the accessibility of material. But apart from the fact that comparatively few persons can have the advantage of easy recourse to a comprehensive collection, the fact is that no library is truly comprehensive; in consequence, mechanisms for sharing resources have been developed, such as interlibrary lending, photocopying services, and telefacsimile. Moreover, within each library numerous circumstances affect the accessibility of its collection — the state of preservation of its stock, which involves such matters as the adequacy of its binding and rebinding program, the deterioration of paper in its stock, the shelving arrangements, safeguarding from pilferage, for example.

One project completed during the past year had to do with the planning of acquisitions programs in the libraries of a national university system; others continued to deal with the preservation of library materials; still others related to methods of storage and reproduction; two new projects concerned the furnishing of library buildings.

Resources of Canadian University Libraries. Several years ago the Library Survey Committee of the National Conference of Canadian Universities and Colleges recommended that, in order to correct deficiencies in the collections of Canadian academic libraries for research in the humanities and social sciences, a plan for institutional specialization be developed. It was suggested that, as a first step, there be an independent outside survey of existing resources and needs. Such a survey, made possible by a grant from the Council, was conducted by Edwin E. Williams, Counsellor on Collections of the Harvard University Library, long associated with the development of the Farmington Plan for Cooperative Acquisition of Foreign

Publications in the United States, and the author of the *Farmington Plan Handbook*.⁹

The report of Mr. Williams' survey of 14 major libraries has been published.¹⁰

Among its recommendations are that a program of grants be initiated for supporting major existing collections, and that librarians of Canadian universities work closely with the National Library in planning. After observing that two cornerstones of cooperation — the National Union Catalogue and a union list of serials in the humanities and social sciences — deserve particular attention, establishment of an Office of Canadian Library Resources is recommended. Such an office would encourage avoidance of needless duplication by libraries, work with them on plans for building up their collections of books and microreproductions in the national interest, and help them compete in the world's book markets for the materials they need.

The W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory. The establishment of this laboratory in August 1961 in the building of the Virginia State Historical Society in Richmond to serve exclusively for the investigation of problems connected with the preservation of library materials, has been recorded in the preceding Annual Report.¹¹ The Laboratory has been concerned especially with three assignments: development of a method for treating bound volumes so as to prevent the deterioration of the paper contained in them; investigation of adhesives used in "adhesive" or "perfect" binding with a view to identifying those having prospect of sufficient permanence and durability to make them acceptable for library use; and research leading to the establishment of performance standards for library binding.

Aerosol Deacidification of Bound Volumes. Previous studies have shown that few books manufactured during the first half of this century will be usable in the next.¹² The principal

⁹ VI: 39.

¹⁰ Edwin E. Williams. *Resources of Canadian University Libraries for Research in the Humanities and Social Sciences. Report of a Survey for the National Conference of Canadian Universities and Colleges.* Ottawa: National Conference of Canadian Universities and Colleges, 1962. 87 pp. (Also an edition in French.)

¹¹ VI: 21-22.

¹² III: 31-32. See also: Randolph W. Church, editor: *Deterioration of Book Stock, Causes and Remedies: Two Studies on the Permanence of Book Paper Conducted by W. J. Barrow.* Richmond: The Virginia State Library, 1959. 70 p.

cause of this deterioration derives from acidic compounds or the sources of such compounds left in the paper by the manufacturing processes. If this acidity could be neutralized, deterioration would at least be delayed. A first proposal for doing this involved taking a book apart, treating the individual leaves, and rebinding it; but this was prohibitively expensive. The Laboratory then experimented with a variety of gaseous and aerosol treatments, and has developed a method which seems feasible. This process has now been transferred to Mr. Barrow's workshop in the Virginia State Library, where it will be tested out under operating conditions in order to secure data regarding procedure and cost. A report will be published.

Adhesives. Bookbinding is a principal object of expense to American libraries. Because it is necessarily all job binding (as contrasted with edition binding), the labor costs are high. Every effort has been made to save expense, with the result that hand-sewn bindings, in typical American libraries, are things of the past, having given way to oversewn or side-sewn bindings which do not permit books to open flat. In the very home of the book, the book is itself a cripple, technically and aesthetically.

"Adhesive" or "perfect" binding offers a possible exit from this dilemma. In this form of binding (which has been made familiar by telephone directories) the folds of the leaves are sheared, and a flexible hinge is provided by adhesive. Unfortunately, many of these adhesives have very short lives (often limited to a few months), and knowledge about adhesives is insufficient to permit the prescription of the characteristics which will assure permanence adequate for library acceptance. It is this problem which the Laboratory has attacked.¹³

It was necessary first to develop testing equipment and methods. Then a series of adhesives was tested. These tests brought factors to attention which had previously escaped notice, and this in turn contributed to still further improvement of testing equipment and procedure. Various adhesives were formulated, making use of knowledge won. As the end of the Laboratory's second year approached it had identified certain

¹³ Lee E. Grove: *Adhesive Bookbinding: A Practice Reviewed*. *Library Resources & Technical Services* 6: 143-160. Spring 1962.

characteristics predictive of length of life, and was in sight of an adhesive possessing the desired qualities.

Performance Standards for Library Binding. The standards for library binding are currently based upon specification of materials and workmanship. While these standards perform yeoman service, they are nevertheless related only by conjecture to expected performance. The Bookbinding Committee of the American Library Association has been anxious to be able to specify a binding in terms of the desired performance rather than in terms of the materials used, and in 1961 prepared the ground for a study to develop the necessary standards. After investigating the various places at which this study might be carried out, it was assigned to the Laboratory under the auspices of the Library Technology Project of the American Library Association and under the supervision of an Advisory Committee representing this Association and the Special Libraries Association.¹⁴

Again, an initial requirement was to develop testing devices and procedures. The purpose of a laboratory test is to simulate, in hours, what will happen to the object tested in the course of actual use over perhaps many years, so as to be able to predict its future performance. At the commencement of the investigation there was no test or testing equipment which would reproduce the wear and tear which bindings receive in actual use in libraries. The Laboratory has achieved signal success in remedying this deficiency. Meanwhile it was examining large quantities of worn bindings to discover the insignia of imperfect performance and to estimate the comparative importance of various elements in the binding structure. As a next stage, a number of copies of test bindings have been placed at hard-usage points in a number of libraries so as to validate the predictive test developed in the Laboratory. Such validation will make it possible to prescribe for the components of a binding so as to enable it to meet tests predictive of the desired amount of expected use.

Book Paper. The Laboratory has also continued, though not as a major project, to perform some work connected with the permanence and durability of book paper. This has resulted in a contribution to the testing technique for acidity and in

¹⁴ VI: 22. Also, Frazer G. Poole: Performance Standards in Library Binding: *Book Production Magazine* 75: 67-68. June 1962.

the development of a method for rapidly evaluating test results.¹⁵

Further details of the Laboratory's work during its first two years are presented in a report which it has issued.¹⁶

A National Plan for Preservation of Deteriorating Materials. It has long been known that much manuscript and printed material of importance to scholars is rapidly deteriorating and that both the originals and their contents will be lost unless the rate of special preservation is sharply increased within the near future.

At least one important public library is currently expending nearly half as much on preservation as on the acquisition of new books, and the total bill to libraries for preservation is undoubtedly enormous.

To enable a committee of the Association of Research Libraries to secure more concrete knowledge of the extent of the problem, the Council made a previously reported grant for a statistical study.¹⁷ A summary of the findings has been published.¹⁸

A second study, "Development of Programs for the Preservation of Deteriorating Research Library Materials," is now in progress under the auspices of the Association with the Council's support. This is being conducted by Gordon R. Williams, Director of the Midwest Inter-Library Center, and is intended to provide for coordination of all preservation activities so as to avoid unnecessary duplication or the overlooking of significant materials; for bibliographic control of master copies and provision of loanable secondary copies so that scholars will have access to the materials; and for a system for keeping master copies which will assure their permanent storage under optimum conditions and provide for the quick availability of secondary copies at minimum cost.

¹⁵ W. J. Barrow: Hot vs. Cold Extraction Methods for Making a pH Determination. *TAPPI* 46: 468-472, August 1963.

W. J. Barrow: Establishing Least Squares Regression Lines for Data of Aged Paper. *TAPPI* 45: supp. 209A-210A, September 1962.

¹⁶ W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Richmond, Virginia: *Permanence/Durability of the Book: A Two-Year Research Program*. Richmond, 1963. 46 p.

¹⁷ V: 21; VI: 22-23.

¹⁸ Edwin E. Williams: Magnitude of the Paper-Deterioration Problem As Measured by a National Union Catalog Sample. *College and Research Libraries* 23: 499, 543. November 1962.

Photostorage. Numerous devices have been developed in recent years for storing informational records in photographic form, usually in microcopy, and for providing prompt access to a desired record. The Council participated actively in the development of one of these devices.¹⁹ None of them has as yet attained general use in libraries. In order to secure a considered study of these mechanisms, the Council early in 1961 commissioned a state-of-the-art review of mechanized information selection and facsimile retrieval systems from the National Bureau of Standards.²⁰ The report, published this past year, is based on a survey conducted by the Bureau's Research Information Center and Advisory Service on Information Processing.²¹ The report describes fifteen specific systems employing search-type selection principles. In addition, microfilm aperture-card systems and related devices used for address-location retrieval are discussed at shorter length. The report also contains a chapter on historical background and a bibliography of several hundred references.

Microfilm as a Storage Medium. Several years ago, when the John Crerar Library was planning to move to its new building on the campus of the Illinois Institute of Technology, it was hoped that additional storage space might be acquired, when the need might arise, through microfilming older files of periodicals.²² In order to explore the economics of this proposal, the Council commissioned from the firm of Forbes & Waite a study of the cost of microfilming 100,000 bound volumes of periodicals.²³ In an article subsequently published, this study was used to compare the cost of microfilming versus that of new construction for the storage of originals.²⁴ It was found that under most circumstances, even if the cost of the negative were shared by a number of libraries, new construction would be less expensive than microfilming. However, this

¹⁹ VI: 25-28.

²⁰ V: 24.

²¹ C. Bagg and M. E. Stevens: *Information Selection Systems Retrieving Replica Copies: A State-of-the-Art Report*. Washington; U. S. Government Printing Office, 1962, iv, 172 p. (National Bureau of Standards Technical Note 157).

²² H. Henkle: Crerar Library Use of Microfilm in Science Information Service. National Microfilm Association: *Proceedings* 10: 74-78. 1961.

²³ V: 23-24.

²⁴ V. W. Clapp and R. T. Jordan: Re-evaluation of Microfilm As a Method of Book Storage. *College and Research Libraries* 24: 5-15. January 1963.

situation might easily be altered, e.g. by changes in the density of storage of the original material, or by changes in the ratio of reduction used in microfilming.

Enlargements from Microcopy. "Reader-printers," devices with which microcopy may be consulted but which also permit making enlarged copies of selected images, have come into use in the past few years. To evaluate these devices the Library Technology Project commissioned a study of them by William R. Hawken which was published during the past year.²⁵

Hand-Viewer for Microcopy. Previous reports have followed the progress of an attempt to develop an inexpensive and portable hand-viewer to enable an individual to read microcopy comfortably without dependence upon an expensive institutionalized machine.²⁶

The attempt encountered a number of obstacles. One of these was to bring enough light to impinge on the object; this was early and satisfactorily solved.

A second obstacle stemmed from the fact that the field of view of a magnifier varies inversely with its magnifying power, and that, in consequence, if a lens is capable of enlarging the reduced image of a page to its original size, it is incapable of viewing the entire width of the page. For this reason, microcopy hand-viewers sacrifice magnifying power to field of view. The result is that the user sees the page at less than its original size, and, since he is viewing with but one eye, he is doubly discomfited. The Council's efforts to overcome this obstacle by improved lens design have not been successful.

The most recent attempt to overcome this obstacle employed the principle of the compound microscope, in which the objective lens and the eye-piece are separated. The prototype resulting from this attempt was received during the past year. It is successful in providing the desired magnification and field of view; it also provides working distance from the object sufficient to permit adequate illumination of the object, and sufficient eye-relief to permit the user to wear glasses. But the exit-pupil, i.e., the bundle of light rays emerging from the eye-

²⁵ W. R. Hawken: *Enlarged Prints from Library Microforms. A Study of Processes, Equipment and Materials.* Chicago, Library Technology Project, American Library Association [1963]. 131 p.

²⁶ IV: 31-37; V: 25.

PROTOTYPE OF READER FOR MICROCOPY — The hand-viewer, employing the principle of the compound microscope and with detachable folding plastic base, provides adequate magnification, field of view, working distance and eye relief, but permits so little latitude of eye-positioning as to be uncomfortable to use.

piece, has so small a diameter (approximately 1/8th inch) that the user has no latitude for movement but must maintain a completely rigid and fixed relation to the viewer — the very opposite of comfort. It may be said, in consequence, that this avenue of approach to individual use of microcopy has been exhausted.

Automatic book-cradle/page-turner. The need for a reliable automatic page-turner emerged during the experiment with closed-circuit TV between library installations on the campus of the University of Virginia in 1957-1958, when it was found that there was no satisfactory device for enabling a user at a distance to turn the pages of the book being scanned by the TV camera at the transmitting station.²⁷ But, in addition to its potential uses in the transmission of material by TV or telefacsimile, it was argued that an automatic page-turner might increase the efficiency of microfilming. In addition, because it would be possible to construct a page-turner in which the book would be held at a 90° angle instead of flat, it was hoped that it might assist in avoiding the considerable risk of damage to bindings which microfilming in the flat position entails.²⁸

The device resulting from this development, to which a microfilm camera is attached, was completed and delivered during the past year. It was placed for field testing in the New York Public Library. The tests disclosed certain mechanical and optical deficiencies. In addition to these, however, it did not appear that the device is yet capable of operating without supervision so as to make the work of the microfilm camera operator more productive. Further tests are planned.

Microstorage in Crystals. Taking advantage of the physical characteristics which give rise in certain crystals to the "crystal color center phenomenon," it is believed to be possible to record information in these crystals at a density of a thousand bits per millimeter in three dimensions. This is 10¹² bits per cubic centimeter, or, roughly, the amount of information contained in a quarter of a million books. It is also believed to be possible similarly to store information in graphic form, although not with equal density.

The Carson Laboratories of Bristol, Connecticut, have

²⁷ I: 22-23; II: 24; IV: 17; VI: 29-30.

²⁸ VI: 29-30.

undertaken, in a preliminary investigation, to demonstrate for the Council the recording, storage and reading-out at high resolution of graphic information, making use of this capability. The potential usefulness for library work is not so much the high density of storage as the fact that both recording and reading-out are effected with radiant energy at very high speeds, offering the promise of inexpensiveness of creation, dissemination, storage and recovery of the record.

Copying Devices. During the past year a contract was awarded to Photogrammetry, Inc., of Rockville, Maryland, for the design and fabrication of prototypes of a camera for the production of microcopies without laboratory processing, together with a monocular viewer for using such microcopies. Simplicity and reliability of operation, portability, convenient availability of film, and low cost per page copied are among the characteristics sought. As of the end of the fiscal year a breadboard adaptation of a Polaroid camera had been designed and manufactured which appears to be easy to operate and to have good copying ability.

A contract was also given to the Institute for Scientific Information, Philadelphia, for a feasibility study of the application of fiber optics — the use of minute but flexible threads of light-conducting material — to the development of a device for the selective copying of passages from books.

Library Buildings. The book on the planning of college and university library buildings, being written under the auspices of the Association of Research Libraries and the Association of College and Research Libraries by Mr. Keyes D. Metcalf, Director Emeritus of the Harvard University Library, a grant for which was previously reported,²⁹ has progressed to the point at which a contract has been signed with a publisher looking to publication in the autumn of 1964. Meanwhile, a number of the chapters of the book have appeared in preliminary form as journal articles.³⁰

Also, as reported on a later page, the Library Technology Project has arranged for preparation of manuals on library furniture and floor coverings.

²⁹ IV: 20.

³⁰ Keyes D. Metcalf: Alternatives to a New Library Building. *College and Research Libraries* 22: 345-354, 362, September 1962; Compact Shelving. *Ibid.* 23: 103-111, March 1962; Seating Accommodations. *Ibid.* 23: 375-382, September 1962; Traffic Patterns. *Ibid.* 24: 19-30, January 1963; Library Lighting. *Library Journal* 86: 4081-4085, December 1, 1961.

III. LIBRARY ADMINISTRATION

Insuring the Library. Much of the record of civilization is in the custody of libraries, and their executive officers are conscious of their responsibility to protect these records as best they can from damage or destruction by fire, water, vandalism, and other dangers. And, if or when harm comes to the record (and the North American library world annually averages a million dollar loss from fires), they should be able to minimize that harm at the least possible expense. To do so, however, requires knowledge in two rather highly specialized fields: fire protection engineering and insurance. Usually the best informed advisors have an interest in selling equipment or insurance policies and cannot be expected to share the librarian's concern for adequate protection at minimum cost. Even the few disinterested experts in fire protection and insurance have not given adequate attention to the problem of libraries. Insurance industry statistics on losses by fire have not recorded the incidence of fire in libraries, but include public libraries in the category of "public buildings" and include special libraries with the commercial, manufacturing or scientific establishments which they serve. Nor has there been until recently an insurance policy which reflected the special needs and problems of libraries.

Fire tests of library bookstacks about four years ago produced contradictory results and touched off a controversy over the utility of installing automatic sprinklers in library stacks. The controversy also resulted in widely differing views concerning insurance rates. These incidents pointed out sharply the need for more concrete and more detailed information about the perils of fire and other damage, measures to prevent or limit them, and insurance. Consequently, a study was commissioned from a firm of consulting engineers expert in both fire protection and insurance.³¹ The study was sponsored by the Library Technology Project of the American Library Association and was aided by an advisory committee. The investigation resulted in publication of a manual providing the librarian with adequate information about the basic factors affecting risks of damage, enabling him to develop an

³¹ V: 21.

Public Archives of Canada photos

AFTERMATH OF FIRE—When rain penetrated to the electrical system in the building of the Canadian Parliament in 1952 fire resulted. Flames did not get to the Library itself but the collections suffered serious damage from water. The photograph at the top shows book chutes hastily erected to speed removal of books and a dehumidifier. In the picture below pamphlets are drying on stretched lines and books are spread out with sections separated by sticks.

intelligent program of protection.³² The manual also presents a model insurance policy for libraries extensively annotated with comments, explanatory notes and illustrations. This policy is already available to a limited extent, and efforts will be made to make it generally available.

Library Statistics. The earliest important compilation of statistics of libraries in the United States was published by the Smithsonian Institution in 1850. Other compilations appeared only sporadically after that date. In 1936 the U. S. Office of Education was given responsibilities for assembling and publishing such statistics currently. But various circumstances have never favored the execution of this assignment, a principal one of which has been the lack of agreement among libraries on standards of measurement. Do ten pamphlets bound into one volume count as one or ten? Does a university law library count as a separate library or a branch? How is a collection of originals equated with one composed of microcopies? How are reference services measured — by the number of questions answered or the time spent in answering them? What is the common measure of cataloging in a small public library and in a specialized scholarly library?

For want of an adequate central source of comprehensive, authoritative and promptly available statistics, less comprehensive services have attempted to supply the deficiency; at a recent count there were 140 such services.

For several years the Special Libraries Association, American Library Association and Library Services Branch of the U. S. Office of Education have been exploring methods for remedying this situation. As a result, arrangements have been made by which Mr. Joel Williams, Chief of the Statistical Services Division, Educational Statistics Branch, U. S. Department of Health, Education and Welfare, is being given a year's leave of absence to prepare a handbook of accepted practice for the gathering and presentation of library statistics, with the assistance of an advisory committee representing the American Library Association, Special Libraries Association, American Standards Association and the Library Services Branch, U. S.

³² *Protecting the Library and Its Resources. A Guide to Physical Protection and Insurance. Report on a Study Conducted by Gage-Babcock & Associates, Inc.* Chicago, Library Technology Project, American Library Association, [1963]. xv, 322 p. Ill. LTP Publications No. 7.

Office of Education, among others. A grant from the Council for this study has been supplemented by the National Science Foundation, while the National Library of Medicine is providing office space.

"American Library Laws." Since 1943, when the most recent compilation was published of the laws affecting library work in the United States, the amount of such legislation has greatly increased, as has also the need for once more bringing it together. By reproducing the texts of the statutes in photo-facsimile, the Committee on Legislation of the American Library Association will, in a new edition, be able not only to save the expense of type composition and proofreading, but also assure accuracy of transcription. It is proposed to keep the new edition up to date by the issuance of biennial supplements.

University Libraries. The improvement of the administrative arrangements in university libraries has been the object of one project completed and of another initiated during the past year.

Late in 1961 the Council made a grant to the Association of State Institutions of Higher Education in Colorado for an investigation of the feasibility of improving the services of the state's academic libraries through the development of cooperative enterprises and activities.³³ The investigation has been completed and a report published.³⁴ The report recommends that a centralized processing center be established at the University of Colorado to provide technical services for the seven state-supported colleges and universities and an eighth college being established in Pueblo. The report also recommends, among other things, establishment of a teletype network among the principal library centers of the state and the development of rapid means of book-delivery, by motor vehicle or otherwise, between the members of the group.

To the Columbia University Libraries a grant was made to assist in procuring an operations analysis of a university library with the ultimate objective of improving administration.

³³ VI: 39.

³⁴ Donald E. Oehlerts: *A Study to Determine the Feasibility of Establishing a Cooperative Technical Processing Program and Direct Transmission of Interlibrary Loans.* Foreword by Le Moyne W. Anderson. Denver, Colorado: Association of State Institutions of Higher Education in Colorado, 1962. x, 45 p.

The investigation is seeking to identify the major activities involved in the operation of a research library, the kinds and levels of skills and competences involved in each activity, the proportions of intellectual, clerical and manual contribution to each activity, and the effects of changes on various parts of the system. To assist the project there are available, from within the University, facilities for the development and testing of mathematical models of the operation and for linear programming.

Small Public Libraries. In the Council's *Fifth Annual Report*, a grant to the American Library Association for improvement of public library administration in communities serving 10,000 or fewer persons was reported.³⁵ The vehicle for this improvement was to be a series of pamphlets which would serve as guides to these librarians — most of whom have had no professional training — and their boards of trustees. The publication of the last three pamphlets and a final report in the spring of 1963 completed the Small Libraries Project.³⁶ Altogether, 16 pamphlets plus supplementary material and the final report were published and in all but two instances distributed through state library agencies in a total of about 9,400 sets. California and Hawaii were the two exceptions and distribution for these two states was handled through other channels. The history of the project, including the manner in which a number of states have conducted successful programs for small libraries based on the pamphlets, is related in the final report.

³⁵ p. 26-27.

³⁶ *The Small Public Library. A Series of Guides for the Community Librarian and Trustee.* Chicago: Small Libraries Project, Library Administration Division, American Library Association. Titles and authors of the pamphlets are: 1. *The Public Library: A Tool for Modern Living*, Helen E. Wessells; 2. *The Small Public Library — Its Establishment, Organization, and Development*, John C. Frantz; 3. *The Trustee of a Small Public Library*, Virginia C. Young; 4. *The Library Staff*, June S. Smith; 5. *Building and Maintaining the Small Library Collection*, Orilla T. Blackshear; 6. *Organizing the Library's Book Collection*, L. Marion Moshier; 7. *Organizing for Good Library Service*, Joseph F. Shubert; 8. *Reader's Guidance Service in a Small Public Library*, Helen Huguenor Lyman; 9. *Reference Services in a Small Public Library*, Hannah Severns; 10. *Library Service for Adults*, Ruth W. Gregory; 11. *Young Adult Service in a Small Public Library*, Lora Landers; 12. *Children's Services in a Small Public Library*, Winifred Ragsdale; 13. *The Small Library Building*, Joseph L. Wheeler; 14. *The Library in the Small Community*, Edith Foster; 15. *Telling the Library Story*, Marian Walcott; 16. *Cooperative Approach to Library Service*, Hannis S. Smith. In addition there are 16 supplements and the final report.

The welcome which the series has received has been very gratifying. Although it is now generally agreed that the independent small public library is an outworn institution which should be incorporated into a regional system serving not less than 250,000 population, yet the fact remains that there are many thousands of these libraries which are not likely to be incorporated into larger systems in the immediate future, one reason being that they do not realize the benefits to be gained. To such libraries these pamphlets are not only of immediate assistance but may be expected to provide stimulus for seeking the improved basis of service derivable from participation in a larger effort.

When the usefulness of the series became apparent after several test demonstrations, sets were requested by Canadian libraries. The grant was increased to make the distribution of more than one thousand sets in Canada possible through the provincial libraries. The Province of Quebec has requested and has been given permission to translate the series into French.

Individual complimentary sets have been sent to a score of libraries abroad upon their request.

The Small Libraries Project, as originally proposed by Mr. Joseph L. Wheeler, the director emeritus of the Enoch Pratt Free Library (Baltimore), was intended to develop methods of work simplification for use in small libraries. This aspect was omitted from the project because it was felt that attention should not be diverted from the main task of preparing a series of manuals covering the whole range of small library operations.

However, Mr. Wheeler has continued to concern himself with work simplification, and with his collaboration the Graduate School of Library Service of Drexel Institute of Technology developed during the past year the plan for a study, which the Council is supporting, for preparing a manual on the procedural techniques involved in the selection, acquisition, cataloging and classification, processing, circulation and mending of books in libraries serving communities of populations of 25,000 or less. In the study a number of small libraries in nearby Pennsylvania, New Jersey and Delaware will serve as laboratories for studying the procedures and for devising and testing best practices.

University-School-Community Library Coordination. In 1960 the Council made a grant to Brown University to investigate the means by which library service to education in the State of Rhode Island could be improved. The investigation resulted in a report by John A. Humphry, Director of the City Library of Springfield, Massachusetts, assisted by Lucille Wickersham, Assistant Director of the same library, published this past spring.³⁷ The report, which was prepared under the immediate sponsorship of the University's Master of Arts in Teaching Program, recommended sweeping changes in numerous aspects of library service within the State, some of which will require legislative action. Of the report *The Providence Journal* said that it "shows that it is better to light a candle than to curse the dark."³⁸

The report represents but one — though an important — step in an effort to improve the library resources of the State. A next step is to effect adoption of its recommendations. The Council has made a small supplemental grant to assist in securing the necessary public attention and support.

School Libraries. Following the development of minimum *Standards for School Library Programs 1960* by the American Association of School Librarians of the American Library Association in cooperation with a number of other national library and educational groups, the Council in September 1960 made a grant to assist promotion of the standards through preparation of informational material, conferences and other measures.³⁹ The project was conducted from February 1, 1961, to July 31, 1962, and a final report has been published.⁴⁰ Meanwhile, recognizing the success of the initial work, the Knapp Foundation has made a grant for continuation of the project in a revised form.

A second project in school library development was also completed this past fiscal year with the aid of a previously

³⁷ John A. Humphry with the special assistance of Lucille Wickersham: *Library Cooperation, The Brown University Study of University-School-Community Library Coordination in the State of Rhode Island.* Providence, Rhode Island: Brown University Press, 1963. 228 p.

³⁸ March 29, 1963, p. 29.

³⁹ V: 27.

⁴⁰ Mary Frances Kennon and Leila Ann Doyle: *Planning School Library Development, A Report of the School Library Development Project, American Association of School Librarians, February 1, 1961 - July 31, 1962.* Chicago, American Library Association, 1962. 89 p.

announced grant from the Council.⁴¹ This project was a survey of the school libraries of Puerto Rico, conducted by Mary V. Gaver, Professor of Library Service at Rutgers — The State University, and Gonzalo Velázquez, Director of Libraries in the Department of Education of the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico. Their survey was made with the cooperation of the Department of Education, which is administratively responsible for school libraries and librarians (who are also teachers), the Sociedad de Bibliotecarios de Puerto Rico, and others. Puerto Rico endeavors to retain its Spanish heritage, but English is taught as a second language and the school library collections are bilingual, but, the surveyors found, less than adequate both in quantity and quality. Improvement of their content is the subject of principal recommendations contained in the published report.⁴² Among other recommendations which appear possible of attainment within the next few years are betterment of professional training, replacement of obsolete and worn out books, larger minimum collections, and establishment of libraries in schools with an enrollment of 1,000 or more students which do not have libraries now.

The Independent Historical Societies. “Few books of American history are published today without some expression of the author’s gratitude to one of the older state historical societies for assistance or for permission to publish manuscripts in their possession,” Walter Muir Whitehill observes in the preface of his *Independent Historical Societies*.⁴³ Despite their services to historical research, the independent societies, deriving their support exclusively from private sources, are falling behind in their tasks of assembling, organizing and making available the materials for American history. How to remedy the situation? By seeking appropriations as public institutions? By engaging in programs for the popularization of history? Or are there other ways?

To probe these questions the Council made a grant in 1958 for the study represented by this book, under the sponsorship

⁴¹ VI: 40.

⁴² Mary V. Gaver and Gonzalo Velázquez: *School Libraries of Puerto Rico, A Survey and Plan for Development*. The Authors, 1963, [x], 116 p.

⁴³ Walter Muir Whitehill: *Independent Historical Societies, An enquiry into their research and publication functions and their financial future*. Boston: The Boston Athenaeum, 1962. Distributed by Harvard University Press. xviii, 593 p.

of four of the oldest historical societies — the Massachusetts Historical Society, the American Antiquarian Society, the Historical Society of Pennsylvania and the Virginia Historical Society.⁴⁴

Mr. Whitehill's report describes, in brilliant selection of detail, the background and current activities of the principal independent societies as well as a number of publicly-supported institutions. The seeking of public funds by the independent societies for their general support is not advocated by Mr. Whitehill, but "public assistance in specific projects of scholarly utility, such as microfilming newspapers and local records, for example, could be both appropriate and helpful."

The Library Technology Project. The Council has continued its support of this project, the purpose of which is to improve technological applications to library work through testing and evaluation of supplies and equipment, promotion of standards and preparation of specifications, development of new devices, and the conduct of an information service to libraries on all these matters.⁴⁵ Activities of LTP, which operates under the auspices of the American Library Association and the supervision of an advisory committee in which the Special Libraries Association is represented, are reflected in its annual reports, in a monthly bulletin of information which it publishes in the *ALA Bulletin* and in *Special Libraries*, and, as well, in special publications or monographs describing the results of testing, standardizations and development.

Two such special publications of the past year have been previously mentioned — the reports on *Enlarged Prints from Library Microforms* (supra, p. 25) and on *Protecting the Library and its Resources* (supra, p. 29-31).

Among the new undertakings this past year have been:

1. A state-of-the-art report on microfiches, or sheet microfilm, by William R. Hawken, of Berkeley, California, which it is hoped will promote uniformity in what is now a rather confused development due to a number of manufacturers each offering a product incompatible with others. If the number of sizes of microfiches and the number of pieces of equipment required to deal with the various sizes can be limited, it will obviously be of benefit to libraries.

⁴⁴ III: 42.

⁴⁵ III: 39; IV: 20-21; V: 27-28; VI: 34-36.

2. Preparation of a manual on library furniture, including specifications and performance standards, by Martin Van Buren, of Charlotte, North Carolina, designer and library consultant, and Stephen D. Pryce, of Grand Rapids, Michigan, who has had many years experience in the manufacture of furniture.

3. Preparation of a manual on floors and floor coverings for libraries, by Foster D. Snell, Inc., New York City.

Also under way under the auspices of the Project are a number of activities, including among others the previously-mentioned development of performance standards for library bookbinding, the preparation of a report describing and evaluating various methods for reproducing catalog cards, the development of a book-labeling device, a study of adhesives, and the promotion of the use of permanent/durable book paper.

An attempt was made by the Library Technology Project during the year to realize one of the earliest proposals for the Council's work, the establishment of a permanent showroom for library equipment and devices. It was found that even with the initial advantages of good location (in mid-town Chicago) and low rent the prospective continuing costs were too high to justify the undertaking.

Standardization in Library Work. For the second year the Council matched a grant by the National Science Foundation to support the work of Sectional Committee Z39, Standards in Library Work and Documentation, of the American Standards Association. This Committee brings together the viewpoints of librarians, the world of scholarship, publishers and editors, and works with counterpart committees in other national standards organizations as well as the International Standards Organization on the development of standards which affect all these groups. During the past two years it has brought to completion the draft of a national standard for abbreviation of periodical titles, it has reached accord with the British Standards Institution on the transliteration of Cyrillic into the English alphabet, it has achieved progress in the development of standards of transliteration for Arabic, Greek, Hebrew and Japanese, and has pursued work on standards for machine coding, bibliographic references, abstracts, terminology and library statistics.⁴⁶

⁴⁶ A. J. Richter: Z-39 Today: Its Work and Its Subcommittees. *Special Libraries* 54: 107-109, February 1963.

IV. PLANNING

Automation in Libraries. Partly as a result of studies supported by the Council, interest in automation in libraries has increased rapidly and has recently reached much higher levels of comprehension, both on the part of librarians and of engineers, than was previously the case. During the past year it seemed desirable to take advantage of this situation and to bring together a number of librarians and engineers from among those most informed or most interested to discuss the present posture with the hope that from the discussion might emerge improved understandings hastening next steps.

Accordingly, at the suggestion of the National Science Foundation a Conference on Libraries and Automation was held at the Airlie Foundation near Warrenton, Virginia, May 26-29, 1963 under the joint sponsorship of the Library of Congress, the National Science Foundation and the Council. The series of working papers that was commissioned proved exceptionally effective, and the meeting is believed to have achieved its purpose. The Library of Congress, which organized the meeting, will publish the working papers and proceedings.

Libraries and Urban Development. With assistance from the Council, a Symposium on Library Functions in the Changing Metropolis was held May 27-29, 1963 at Endicott House near Cambridge under the joint sponsorship of the National Book Committee and the Joint Center for Urban Studies of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology and Harvard University to explore the role of libraries in urban life and their place in urban planning. A number of prominent librarians and social scientists participated.⁴⁷ A follow-up on the meeting is planned.

Research on Concepts and Problems of Libraries of the Future. The Council's *Sixth Annual Report* described the circumstances which led to the placing, effective November 1, 1961, of a contract with Bolt Beranek & Newman Inc. of Cambridge, Massachusetts for "research on concepts and problems of libraries of the future" to be directed, in con-

⁴⁷ Dialogue in Dedham? A Report on the Symposium on Library Functions in the Changing Metropolis, May 27-29, 1963. *Wilson Library Bulletin* 38: 50-64, September 1963.

sultation with an advisory committee [see p. 5], by Dr. J. C. R. Licklider.⁴⁸

The first year's work under the contract proposed to develop an agenda for further research through a number of preliminary inquiries, the results of some of which it was expected might be publishable.

For the second year, still in progress, the investigation was narrowed to the consideration of two principal topics — "memory organization" and "man-machine symbiosis."

A number of reports are resulting from the study, one of which has been published.⁴⁹ Others are expected to be published in the near future.

⁴⁸ VI: 10-11.

⁴⁹ John A. Swets: Information Retrieval Systems. *Science* 141: 245-250. July 19, 1963.

Other reports and memoranda include:

Black, F.: Specific-Question-Answering System. 21 January 1963. 26 p.

Dobrow, Daniel G.: Syntactic Analysis of English by Computer. 19 August 1963. 55 p.

Grignetti, Mario: On the Length of a Class of Serial Files: June 1963. 24 p.

Licklider, J. C. R.: "Ontogeny", an Approach to Machine Comprehension of Natural Language. 31 January 1962. 19 p.

Marill, Thomas: Semantic Nets: Informal Introduction. 5 March 1963. 15 p.

—: Two Concepts of a Library. 16 April 1962. 11 p.

Raphael, B.: Question Answering Systems and Memory Organization. 16 January 1963. 8 p.

Senders, John W.: Estimates of the Information Content of the World's "Literature". March 1963. 6 p.

Swets, John A.: Measures of Effectiveness of Information Retrieval Systems: A Review and a Proposal. March 1963. 23 p.

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Accountant's Opinion

August 20, 1963

To the Board of Directors of

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements present fairly the assets, liabilities and the fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1963 and its expenditures and income for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles applied on a basis consistent with that of the preceding year. Our examination of these statements was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
STATEMENT OF ASSETS, LIABILITIES
AND FUND BALANCE

June 30, 1963

ASSETS

Cash		\$ 84,348
Investments:		
United States Treasury Bills due August 1, 1963, at cost plus discount earned (approximate market)	\$ 199,500	
Savings account, including earned interest for the year of \$41,939	<u>1,057,343</u>	1,256,843
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation in annual instalments of \$1,000,000 (Note)		6,000,000
Deposits		<u>475</u>
		<u>\$7,341,666</u>

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Grants and contracts payable (see accompanying statement)		\$ 797,240
Accounts payable and withheld taxes		2,620
Fund balance:		
Balance June 30, 1962	\$7,601,403	
Deduct — Expenditures less income for the year (see accompanying statement)	<u>1,059,597</u>	
Balance June 30, 1963 (Note)		<u>6,541,806</u>
		<u>\$7,341,666</u>

NOTE

The terms of the Grant from The Ford Foundation provide that \$200,000 annually is earmarked to assist the Council "to concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval of information through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized scientific personnel." At June 30, 1963 \$1,200,000 of the Fund Balance is earmarked for this purpose. Also, \$645,852 has been appropriated for specific grants and contracts and \$13,245 has been allocated to the President for future grants and contracts to be made at his discretion.

STATEMENT OF EXPENDITURES AND INCOME

For the Year Ended June 30, 1963

EXPENDITURES

Grants, contracts and Council-administered projects (see accompanying statement)	\$985,203	
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants awarded (see accompanying statement)	<u>23,638</u>	\$ 961,565
General administrative expense:		
Compensation and employee benefits	117,877	
Rent	7,500	
Professional services	3,420	
Travel and meetings	9,694	
Furniture and equipment	196	
Supplies, printing, insurance, communications and other	<u>12,474</u>	<u>151,161</u>
		\$1,112,726

INCOME

From investments	<u>53,129</u>
Expenditures less income	<u><u>\$1,059,597</u></u>

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

Year Ended June 30, 1963

	Payable June 30, 1962	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1963
American Association of Law Libraries					
Advisory committee on Project Lawsearch.....		\$ 5,000		\$ 5,000	
A mechanized compilation of a list of legal subject headings		3,000		3,000	
American Bar Foundation					
Automatic indexing of legal literature.....		35,000		20,000	\$ 15,000
American Institute of Biological Sciences					
Continuation of experimental publication of a scientific journal in microform.....	\$ 8,724			8,724	
American Library Association					
Assistance to small community libraries.....		33,852		33,852	
Compilation of a new edition of American Library Laws		10,500		10,500	
Completion of ALA Catalog Code		35,100	\$ 1,349	16,201	17,550
Coordination of library statistics.....		48,960		24,480	24,480
Foreign survey of the Dewey Decimal Classification		20,000			20,000
Implementation of the 1960 School Library Standards			2,342	(2,342)	
Library Technology Project					
Development of a microfilm reader-finder....			1,000	(1,000)	
Development of performance standards for library bookbinding — Phase II.....	21,445	18,686		21,445	18,686
Development of plans for a showroom of library furniture and equipment.....		5,000	1,481	3,519	
Extension of Library Technology Project to June 30, 1962.....	44		5,209	(5,165)	
Extension of Library Technology Project to June 30, 1963.....		220,000		186,243	33,757
Projects of testing and standardization....			230	(230)	
Publication of a book-selection service at the college library level.....	150,000				150,000
Support of the ALA International Relations Office	71,716				71,716
American Library Association (co-sponsor with Association of Research Libraries)					
Preparation of a book on the planning of college/university library buildings	35,365				35,365
Arkansas Foundation of Associated Colleges					
Re-evaluation of the co-operative library system of the Arkansas Foundation of Associated Colleges	5,130			5,130	

	Payable June 30, 1962	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1963
Association of Research Libraries					
Development of programs for the preservation of library materials		\$ 11,500		\$ 11,500	
Study of statistical basis for planning the preservation of library materials			\$ 245	(245)	
Association of State Institutions of Higher Education in Colorado					
Study of feasibility of a co-operative technical processing program			495	(495)	
W. J. Barrow Laboratory					
Establishment of a laboratory for investigations relating to preservation of books and other library materials	\$ 61,003			47,122	\$ 13,881
Bell & Howell Company					
Development of a step-and-repeat camera for producing microimages by Xerography.....	106,991			33,549	73,442
Theodore Besterman					
Travel grant-in-aid of compilation of 4th edition of World Bibliography of Bibliographies		3,500		3,500	
Bolt Beranek and Newman, Inc.					
Research on concepts and problems of libraries of the future					
1961 - 1962	114,683			79,542	35,141
1962 - 1963		199,718		106,507	93,211
Brown University					
A study in support of university-school- community library coordination			4,332	(4,332)	
Implementation of recommendations of the Study		4,050		4,050	
Capital Graphic Systems, Inc.					
Feasibility of simplified lithographic process for catalog card reproduction		5,000		1,000	4,000
Carson Laboratories					
Demonstration of high density crystalline photo-storage		51,274			51,274
Columbia University					
Operations analysis of a university library....		7,200		7,200	
The de Florez Company, Inc.					
Field test of automatic book-cradle/ page-turner	1,000	5,000		4,667	1,333
Working model of an automatic book-cradle/ page-turner	745			745	
Working model of a book-copying cradle/press.	682	3,500		3,253	929
Working model of a catalog card duplicator....	1,456	3,000		2,142	2,314
Drexel Institute of Technology					
Preparation of a manual on work simplification in small libraries.....		42,190		21,095	21,095
Expenses of testing a coordinate index to legal literature*					
		5,000	145	787	4,068

* Council-administered project.

	Payable June 30, 1962	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1963
Expenses connected with the study of concepts and problems of libraries of the future*	\$ 1,879			\$ 933	\$ 946
Fairchild Camera & Instrument Corporation					
Feasibility of simplified lithographic process for catalog card reproduction		\$ 5,000	\$ 5,000		
Institute for Scientific Information					
Feasibility study of the Copywriter		10,000			10,000
Intectron Incorporated					
Investigation of factors affecting high-reduction microphotography	1,733			1,000	733
Jonker Business Machines, Inc.					
Construction of production model of Minimatrex Camera		14,000		12,000	2,000
Construction of production model of Minimatrex Reader		7,500		7,500	
Equipment to test a coordinate index to legal literature		7,188		7,188	
Library of Congress					
Creation of a national union catalog of manuscript collections (supplement)		90,000		90,000	
Development of Library of Congress classification for Anglo-American Law	17,100			17,100	
Planning a national conference on mechanization in libraries		2,000		2,000	
Study of possibilities of mechanization in large research libraries	20,000				20,000
John R. Miles Company					
Development of a microscope-magnifier for reading micro-opaques		1,049		1,049	
Music Library Association					
To record the holdings of American libraries for inclusion in the International Inventory of Musical Sources		27,300		13,650	13,650
National Book Committee					
For a conference on libraries and urban social problems		5,000		5,000	
National Bureau of Standards					
State-of-the-art-review of mechanized information selection and facsimile retrieval systems			22	(22)	
New York Public Library (on behalf of American Standards Association Sectional Committee Z39 on Library Work and Documentation)					
Development of standards in library work and documentation		8,470		8,470	
Photogrammetry, Inc.					
Design and fabrication of prototypes of a scholar's camera and monocular viewer		8,626			8,626

* Council-administered project

	Payable June 30, 1962	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1963
Project Lawsearch (The Michie Company, Matthew Bender & Company, Inc. and The Bureau of National Affairs, Inc.)					
Development of a disseminable, mechanical information search system for legal literature	\$ 5,000			\$ 5,000	
Queens Borough Public Library					
Study of feasibility of a library exhibit at New York World's Fair, 1964-5		\$ 2,000		2,000	
Society of American Archivists					
A study of state archives	14,000				14,000
Syracuse University					
Development of programs in information storage and retrieval		3,750		3,750	
William H. B. Thomas					
Development of testing program for a coordinate index to legal literature		4,640		4,640	
Thompson Ramo Wooldridge, Inc.					
Studies in word correlation and automatic indexing, Phases I and IIA	22,749		\$ 726	22,023	
University of California					
Development of a computer program for maintaining serial records		12,650		12,650	
University of Chicago					
Study of patterns in the use of research library materials	24,600				\$ 24,600
University of Florida					
Participation by University of Florida in Task Force ABLE (Agricultural, Biological Literature Exploitation)			1,062	(1,062)	
University of Pittsburgh					
Searching statutory law by computer	29,443				29,443
	<u>\$715,488</u>	<u>\$985,203</u>	<u>\$23,638</u>	<u>\$879,813</u>	<u>\$797,240</u>

Reports and Publications
Resulting From or Assisted By
Grants and Contracts / October 1, 1963

Acquisition and Apportionment of Materials

The Farmington Plan

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Robert L. Talmadge: *The Farmington Plan Survey; an Interim Report.* *College and Research Libraries* 19:375-383, September 1958.

Robert Vosper: *Farmington Redivivus: or Ten Years of Coordinated Foreign Book Procurement in the U. S.* *Aslib Proceedings* 11:327-334, December 1959.

—: *International Book Procurement; or, Farmington Extended.* *College and Research Libraries* 21:117-124, March 1960.

Edwin E. Williams: *Farmington Plan Handbook, Revised to 1961 and Abridged.* [Office of the Executive Secretary, Association of Research Libraries, Cornell University Library, Ithaca, New York, 1961.] 140 p.

—: *What Is the Farmington Plan?* [Cambridge, Massachusetts: Farmington Plan Committee of the Association of Research Libraries, 1959.] 4 p.

The United States Book Exchange

Edwin E. Williams: *A Serviceable Reservoir; Report of a Survey of the United States Book Exchange.* Washington, The United States Book Exchange, Inc., 1959. 81 p.

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Mortimer Graves: *A First Anniversary Report of Progress on the Implementation of the Dingell Amendment to Public Law 480 (Title I, Section 104n).* *ACLS [American Council of Learned Societies] Newsletter* 10:8-12, November 1959.

—: *An Addendum Report on the Implementation of the Dingell Amendment to Public Law 480*. Key West, Florida: The Author, March 1960. 4 p.

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Lee E. Grove: Reading for the Blind at a New Frontier. *ALA Bulletin* 53:744, September 1961.

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Hubbard Ballou: Ways to Prepare a "New Shaw" List. In R. E. Kingery and M. F. Tauber, eds.: *Book Catalogs*. New York: Scarecrow Press, Inc., 1963, p. 100-122.

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Bookbinding and Book Repair

Fred W. Alpers: *Library Binding in Europe*. [Cleveland, Ohio, 1961.] 33 p., typescript.

Development of Performance Standards for Library Binding, Phase I: Report of the Survey Team. Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association, 1961. 62 p.

Lee E. Grove: Adhesive Bookbinding: A Practice Reviewed. *Library Resources & Technical Services* 6:143-160, Spring 1962.

—: Predictability of Permanence in "Perfect" Library Bindings. *College and Research Libraries* 22:341-344, September 1961.

[American Library Association. Library Technology Project:] Evaluation of GBC [General Binding Corporation] Laminator. *ALA Bulletin* 56:56-57, January 1962.

—: Manuscript-marking Ink. *Ibid.* 56:361, April 1962.

Gladys T. Piez: Laminator for Libraries. *Ibid.* 53:269-275, March 1961.

—: Some Library Adhesives — A Laboratory Evaluation of P.V.A.'s. [polyvinyl acetates]. *Ibid.* 56:838-843, October 1962.

Frazer G. Poole: Performance Standards in Library Binding. *Book Production Magazine* 75:67-68, June 1962.

Books — Dissemination

Peter S. Jennison and William H. Kurth: *Books in the Americas: A Study of the Principal Barriers to the Booktrade in the Americas.* Washington: Pan American Union, General Secretariat, Organization of American States, 1960. 165 p. [Second printing, 1961.]

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Keyes D. Metcalf: Alternatives to a New Library Building. *College and Research Libraries* 22:345-354, 362, September 1962; Compact Shelving. *Ibid.* 23:103-111, March 1962; Seating Accommodations. *Ibid.* 23:375-382, September 1962 Traffic Patterns. *Ibid.* 24:19-30, January 1963; Library Lighting. *Library Journal* 86:4081-4085, December 1, 1961.

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Richard E. Dolbear: *A Programmed Printer for the High-Speed Production of Catalog Card Sets.* Boston: Edgerton, Germeshausen & Grier, Inc. 1962. 68 p.

Radio Corporation of America. Defense Electronic Products Division: *Final Report. Automatic Enlarging Instant Copy Camera.* [Camden: The Corporation, 1959.] 6 p., 4 pl.

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Andrew D. Osborn: At a German Library Association Conference. *ALA Bulletin* 51:773-775, November 1957. [Account of the meeting of the German Library Association (Verein Deutscher Bibliothekare) Lübeck, June 1957, by the American Library Association's representative.]

—: *Cataloging at the Source; an Opportunity for Cooperation Between the Four Major Book Arts.* Chicago: American Library Association, 1958. 18 p. typescript.

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Nasser Sharify: *Cataloging of Persian Works, Including Rules for Transliteration, Entry and Description*. Chicago: American Library Association, 1959. 161 p. [Second printing, 1961.]

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Wyllis E. Wright: International Cataloging Conference. *Library Resources & Technical Services* 4:85-89, Winter 1960.

Circulation — Procedures

John Diebold & Associates, Inc.: *Preliminary Study of Library Circulation Systems*. [New York] 1959. 31 p. (Also issued as a Microcard.)

George Fry & Associates, Inc.: *Study of Circulation Control Systems, Public Libraries, College and University Libraries, Special Libraries*. Chicago: American Library Association, 1961. 138 p. (Three sections — *Circulation System Selection Manual for Public Libraries, Circulation System Selection Manual for College and University Libraries, Circulation Control for Special Libraries* — have also been published separately.)

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Lyman Chalkley: Conditions for Projection Copying on Dye Cyanide Sensitized Materials. *Photographic Science and Engineering* 3:174-177, July-August 1959.

[Eugene Garfield Associates:] *Final Report on the Development of a First Model of the Copywriter*. Philadelphia, 1960. 11 p., typescript.

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- : *Suggested Topics for State-of-the-Art Reviews*. Washington, 1960. 13 p.
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A C K N O W L E D G M E N T S

The scholar at his book-wheel, which appears on the cover and—in reverse color—on the title-page, is reproduced from an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine . . .*, Paris, 1588. The picture has appeared in previous annual reports of the Council. The picture of the microfilm reader on the cover was taken in the Newspaper Reference Room at the Library of Congress.

The picture of the chained-book library of the University of Leiden, inside the front cover, is taken from *Illustrium Hollandiae & Westfrisiae . . .*, Lvgduni Batavorvm, 1614, and is by Jan Cornelis Woudanus [Jan Cornelisz van 't Woudt], 1570-1615. It is used here by courtesy of The New York Public Library. The second picture appearing inside the front cover is of the interior of the microfilm reading room of the Genealogical Society of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints, in Salt

Lake City, and appears here by courtesy of the Society. The room, incidentally, contains 198 machines and is perhaps the largest such reading room in the United States.

The Library of Congress photograph appearing inside the back cover pictures a battery of microfilm readers in the Newspaper Reference Room at the national library. The contrasting Folger Shakespeare Library photograph shows the interior of the Bodleian Library, Oxford. The picture is taken from *Oxonia Illustrata . . .*, Oxford, 1675, and is by Dav. Loggan, 1635-?1700.

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Council on Library Resources.

Report. 1st-
1956/57-
Washington.

v. 23 cm. annual.

Report year ends June 30.

1. Library science—Research.

Z673.C96A15

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